

GravField: A Participatory Performance Exploring Intercorporeality as Live-Coding Instruments within a Co-located Mixed Reality

1 General Information

- **Performance Title:**

GravField: A Participatory Performance Exploring Intercorporeality as Live-Coding Instruments within a Co-located Mixed Reality

- **Main Contact:**

Botao (Amber) Hu, Reality Design Lab, USA

- **Additional Performers:**

Yuemin Huang, East China Normal University, China

Mingze Chai, Independent, China

Yilan (Elan) Tao, Reality Design Lab, USA

Xiaobo (Aaron) Hu, Reality Design Lab, USA

- **Performance Type:**

Modified Algorave with an additional 10x10m Mixed Reality playground. We will describe the experience in the following context.

2 Abstract

2.1 Introduction

We present "Gravitational Field" (GravField) an experimental and participatory live performance set in a co-located mixed reality environment. Participants wearing AR headsets are invited to join and collectively create real-time music through their collaborative body movements, guided by the programmed

Figure 1: The spectator view of GravField

settings from live-coders. This innovative experiment harnesses intercorporeal signals derived from participants' body movements, including factors like distance, area formation, relative height differences, and head motion synchronization. Live-coders dynamically map these signals into metaphorical audiovisual patterns in augmented reality, providing participants with cues about the relationships between players. The live-coded patterns shape and influence participants' improvisation of body movements, while adjustments in live coding dynamically alter how these movements generate sound, influencing the overall improvisational experience. In addition, spectators outside the live performance area can enjoy the mixed reality performance through projection screens and TVs, enhancing audience engagement. GravField aims to explore the vast potential of intercorporeal signals, creating a communicative, playful, and co-creative space where players' interconnected bodies become the instruments of expression.

2.2 Motivation and related works

In recent years, the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) community has increasingly focused on the experiential body, developing numerous methodologies and tools for designing movement-based interactions. This trend reflects an emphasis on the somatic and artistic relationships produced in the design of interactive systems [6, 7, 10, 11, 8]. To gain a deeper understanding of body expression, researchers use various wearable and mobile technologies to record biodata, then explore methods to transform it into somadata [2]. We are witnessing how the CHI community explores new mechanisms of lived body interaction. The phenomenology of Merleau-Ponty introduces a pivotal concept, intercorporeality

[4, 1] which underscores the profound impact and contribution of intercorporeal interactions in facilitating the sense-making practices within cognitive processes [13]. Therefore, the interpretation of body data should be fluid, focusing on the field created by intercorporeal interaction rather than treating our bodies merely as input-output machines [12]. Some design approaches focus on the active engagement of the body in interaction through sensing, feeling, and intuiting. Loke and Robertson describe this approach as bodily literacy, pointing out the need for a shared language and vocabulary grounded in bodily concepts for collaborative work with the body in design [9, 3]. This approach emphasizes the significance of varying combinations of movement parameters through improvisation to produce and direct movement with greater subtlety and range.

Following this approach, we present an interactive playground involving three immersant improvisers and a live coder who programs a movement-based interactive audio/visual system in an augmented environment, providing a landscape of affordances. We developed a joint improvisation field, gradually created through the conversation between the live coder and the immersants' intercorporeal collaboration.

In contrast to the focus of Francoise et al.'s study on player body movement and sound interaction in live-coding systems [5], our research explores the intercorporeality between multiplayer within a performance context.

Figure 2: The system setting of GravField

2.3 Roles

In this performance, There are four types primary participants: Immersants, Live-Coders, Spectators, as shown in Figure 2.

- Immersants: As primary participants, immersants are dancers equipped with headworn optical see-through Augmented Reality headset, ensuring

Figure 3: The phenomenal concepts of GravField

their connection to the real world and other dancers without isolation or latency. They also see augmented links between dancers, enhancing their awareness of the intercorporeal "field" collaboratively shaped by live-coders and dancers.

- Live-coders: As performers who engage in the real-time creation and manipulation of augmented affordance to generate augmented reality visual and audio pattern. They use programming languages to execute code on the fly.
- Spectators: Equipped with handheld AR devices, Spectators view the performance in real-time, observing the augmented interconnections from a first-person perspective. They can enter the performance field, transforming from passive observers to active participants, blurring the boundaries

between themselves, the dancers, and other spectators.

- Bystander: Those without devices can still engage with "GravField" by watching through a monitor screen, offering a third-person view of the immersive experience. This allows a broader audience to appreciate the complex interplay of connections and movements within the performance.

2.4 Immersant's Experience

When the performance begins, three spectators are invited to wear the AR head-mounted device HoloKit, transforming into 'immersants' in the process. Through the stereoscopic AR display, all immersants perceive themselves as connected by a virtual line. This line assumes a crucial role in our audio-visual system, providing diverse possibilities through its various forms. As the immersants move, the live-coder dynamically generates the line's shape and corresponding sound effects in response to their movements. These audio-visual feedbacks spark the immersants' imagination, fostering whole-body engagement and intercorporeal collaboration with fellow immersants.

2.5 Live-coding Affordances

Live-coders dynamically create affordance patterns based on intercorporeal signals (Fig. 4). Affordances are patterns or structures within the GravField system that respond to specific intercorporeal signals derived from participants' movements. These signals include factors such as distance, area formation, relative height differences, and head motion synchronization. Participants will be introduced to the affordance patterns developed thus far, such as the rope, the spring, and magnetic field patterns.

- The rope affordance pattern (see Fig.4(a)) encourages participants to swing collaboratively to gain maximum feedback. By synchronizing their swinging motions, participants create a continuous and rhythmic audio-visual experience. The chain pattern emphasizes the importance of coordination and shared movement, allowing participants to explore the concepts of rhythm, synchronization, and collective expression. Participants will engage in swinging movements together, experiencing the immersive and captivating nature of the chain pattern in generating collaborative music.
- The spring affordance pattern (see Fig.4 (b)) connects bodies with strong auditory feedback, encouraging participants to play with the distance between them. As participants move closer together, the auditory feedback strengthens, reinforcing their proximity and fostering a sense of unity. Conversely, when participants move apart, the auditory feedback diminishes, prompting them to explore the musical possibilities of distance.

Figure 4: The affordance patterns of GravField

Participants will experiment with the spring pattern, exploring the relationship between distance and sound, and discovering how it influences their collaborative music creation.

- The magnetic field affordance pattern (see Fig.4 (c)) is designed to attract neighboring body relationships. By creating a spatial magnetic vector field between participants, it encourages individual exploration and expression while maintaining a sense of proximity and collaboration. Participants will learn how to utilize the magnetic field pattern to shape the dynamics and interactions between their bodies, creating distinct musical outcomes.

By engaging with these affordance patterns, immersants explore the dynamics and interactions between their bodies, ultimately contributing to the collaborative music creation.

2.6 Audience Engagement

Spectators outside the performance area can observe the mixed reality performance through projection screens and TVs. This allows a broader audience to appreciate the intricate interplay of connections and movements within the performance. By providing spectators with a glimpse into the immersive experience, GravField enhances audience engagement and expands the reach of the performance.

2.7 Conclusion

GravField presents an innovative and participatory live performance that explores the potential of intercorporeal signals in a co-located mixed reality environment. Through collaborative body movements, immersants generate real-time music guided by live-coders' programmed settings. The interplay between intercorporeal signals and live coding shapes the audio-visual experience, fostering a communicative, playful, and co-creative space where interconnected bodies become instruments of expression. By extending the immersive experience to spectators through projection screens and TVs, GravField broadens audience engagement and showcases the complex dynamics of the performance.

3 Video and Audio Materials

Please follow the link below:

<https://vimeo.com/955522087>

4 Program Note

"Gravitational Field" (GravField) is an experimental and participatory live performance set in a co-located mixed reality environment. Participants wearing AR headsets are invited to join and collectively create real-time music through their collaborative body movements, guided by the programmed affordance settings from live-coders. This innovative experiment harnesses intercorporeal signals derived from participants' body movements, including factors like distance, area formation, relative height differences, and head motion synchronization. Live-coders dynamically map these signals into metaphorical audiovisual patterns in augmented reality, providing participants with cues about the relationships between players. The live-coded patterns shape and influence participants' improvisation of body movements, while adjustments in live coding dynamically alter how these movements generate sound, influencing the overall improvisational experience. In addition, spectators outside the live performance area can enjoy the mixed reality performance through projection screens and TVs, enhancing audience engagement. GravField aims to explore the vast potential of intercorporeal signals, creating a communicative, playful, and co-creative space where players' interconnected bodies become the instruments of expression.

5 Artists Biography

- Botao (Amber) Hu is a spatial computing researcher, creative technologist, and media artist. He is the founder of Reality Design Lab, a spatial computing lab. His primary focus lies in XR design theory, with a particular emphasis on co-located multiplayer AR and Cross-Reality. With

expertise in AI, XR, ZKML, robotics, game studies, media theory, and visual design, he has collaborated with renowned companies such as Apple, Twitter, DJI, Google, Microsoft, Pinterest, and thatgamecompany. His works have been featured at top conferences like SIGGRAPH, WWW, CHI, SXSW, TEDx, and received awards including CHI Best Interactivity, Red Dot Design Award, Webby Awards, and Core77 Design Award. He is notably the inventor of HoloKit, an open-source AR headset highly regarded by esteemed research institutions like MIT Media Lab, NYU ITP, Stanford, and Harvard for their mixed reality education and research initiatives. He holds a bachelor's degree in computer science from Tsinghua University and a master's degree in AI from Stanford University.

- Yuemin Huang is a Shanghai-born artist and researcher interested in how culture-constructed media shapes cognition, engaging with themes such as the materiality of digital infrastructure, polycentric self-organizing structures, artistic/technical protocols and constructible perception. Yuemin is also a co-founder of TINAG, an art game group, focusing on experimenting with different organizational structures through games, creating shared experiences within communities, and exploring the alternative reality gaming method. With works appearing in festivals, distributed papers and alternative written forms, including SeP Shanghai(2023), Has-tac(2023), ICA(2023). Yuemin is a lecturer at East China Normal University with the course "Alternative-reality Cross media Game Practice", "Virtual Space and Net Art", and "Physical computation". She holds a bachelor's degree in Public Art from East China Normal University and a master's degree in Art and Technology Studies from the School of the Art Institute of Chicago.
- Mingze Chai is a sound designer, music editor, and sound artist, primarily focusing on audio design within immersive interactive experiences. As a Senior Audio Designer at Bilibili games, Mingze played a key role in the interactive music system and sound design for video game titles such as 'Warm Snow', 'Soda Crisis', 'Higan: Eruthyll', and 'Thrud'. Deeply interested in the intersection of audio artistry and interactive design, his work continuously explores the potential of sound in elevating user experiences.
- Yilan (Elan) Tao is a user-experience designer and architect who specializes in the interaction between people and 3D spaces. She is currently a designer and research assistant at Reality Design Lab, focusing on XR design theory. Her remarkable skills in design and presentation have played a vital role in the success of Reality Design Lab's award-winning projects showcased at top conferences such as CHI, SXSW, ISMAR. She holds a Master's degree from Cornell University.
- Xiaobo (Aaron) Hu is a creative technologist, VJ, and psychological researcher. Currently, he is primarily focused on the intersection of technology and psychology, including but not limited to developing new methods

for psychological measurement and intervention, as well as researching how technological advancements affect societal psychology and moral ethics. Aaron was formerly the head of the innovation lab at 4A Company and has over 10 years of experience in new media, experiential marketing and digital innovation. He is skilled in both software and hardware, adept at delivering optimal technological solutions. He also excels as a bridge between technology and design, collaborating with designers, musicians, and artists to create innovative works.

References

- [1] Phenomenology of Perception - 1st Edition - Maurice Merleau-Ponty - Do. <https://www.routledge.com/Phenomenology-of-Perception/Merleau-Ponty/p/book/9780415834339>.
- [2] ALFARAS, M., TSAKNAKI, V., SANCHES, P., WINDLIN, C., UMAIR, M., SAS, C., AND HÖÖK, K. From Biodata to Somadata. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2020), CHI '20, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1–14.
- [3] CIOLFI FELICE, M., FDILI ALAOUI, S., AND MACKAY, W. E. Knotation: Exploring and Documenting Choreographic Processes. In *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2018), CHI '18, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1–12.
- [4] ERIKSSON, S., UNANDER-SCHARIN, Å., TRICHON, V., UNANDER-SCHARIN, C., KJELLSTRÖM, H., AND HÖÖK, K. Dancing With Drones: Crafting Novel Artistic Expressions Through Intercorporeality. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, May 2019), CHI '19, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1–12.
- [5] FRANÇOISE, J., FDILI ALAOUI, S., AND CANDAU, Y. CO/DA: Live-Coding Movement-Sound Interactions for Dance Improvisation. In *Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2022), CHI '22, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1–13.
- [6] HÖÖK, K., HUMMELS, C., ISBISTER, K., MARTI, P., MÁRQUEZ SEGURA, E., JONSSON, M., MUELLER, F. F., SANCHES, P. A., SCHIPHORST, T., STÅHL, A., SVANAES, D., TROTTO, A., PETERSEN, M. G., AND LIM, Y.-K. Soma-Based Design Theory. In *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, May 2017), CHI EA '17, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 550–557.
- [7] HUMMELS, C., OVERBEEKE, K. C. J., AND KLOOSTER, S. Move to get moved: A search for methods, tools and knowledge to design for expressive and rich movement-based interaction. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing* 11, 8 (Dec. 2007), 677–690.
- [8] LOKE, L., LARSEN, A. T., ROBERTSON, T., AND EDWARDS, J. Understanding movement for interaction design: Frameworks and approaches. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing* 11, 8 (Oct. 2007), 691–701.

- [9] LOKE, L., AND ROBERTSON, T. The lived body in design: Mapping the terrain. In *Proceedings of the 23rd Australian Computer-Human Interaction Conference* (New York, NY, USA, Nov. 2011), OzCHI '11, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 181–184.
- [10] LOKE, L., AND ROBERTSON, T. Moving and making strange: An embodied approach to movement-based interaction design. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction* 20, 1 (Apr. 2013), 7:1–7:25.
- [11] MÁRQUEZ SEGURA, E., TURMO VIDAL, L., ROSTAMI, A., AND WAERN, A. Embodied Sketching. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New York, NY, USA, May 2016), CHI '16, Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 6014–6027.
- [12] MENTIS, H. M., HÖÖK, K., MUELLER, F., ISBISTER, K., KHUT, G. P., AND ROBERTSON, T. Designing for the experiential body. In *CHI '14 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Toronto Ontario Canada, Apr. 2014), ACM, pp. 1069–1074.
- [13] MEYER, C., STREECK, J., AND JORDAN, J. S., Eds. *Intercorporeality: Emerging Socialities in Interaction*. Foundations of Human Interaction. Oxford University Press, New York, NY, 2017.